

Digital Marketing- Consumer Behavior towards Online Shopping

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Abstract

Digitalization gives led to E-commerce: E-commerce has laid to online shopping, which has seen a increase growth amongst global as well as in the Indian context. This paper has the main objective of understanding consumer behavior towards online buying, and to provide suggestions to the E-marketers to fine-tuning their E-businesses’ strategies.

Keywords: consumer awareness, online shopping, problems faced by the buyer, internet usage.

Introduction

Internet is responsible for change in the buying and selling of goods and services throughout of the world. Internet is basically used to pass information, sell the products and collect feedback from the customers. Many companies have started using the internet to cut marketing costs, thereby reducing the price of their products and services to stay forward in highly competitive markets. The customers utilizes the facilities of internet to know the availability of the product, various brand of the products, process of the products, comparing the price of the product, their features and after sale services to buy the product. The internet helps the buyer and the prospective buyer to get necessary information at any point of time. In the blast 10 years business-to-customer E-commerce first evolved. Scholars and practitioners of electronic commerce continuously strive to gain improved insight into consumer behavior in electronic commerce.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the consumers’ awareness about online shopping.
2. To know the various factors which influence the consumer towards online shopping
3. To consider the types of goods purchased online
4. To analyze the consumer’s problem during online shopping
5. To provide recommendations and suggestions.

Sources of Data Collection

For the survey a structured questionnaire is formed in collecting primary data. The questionnaire was distributed to 100 online customers belong to different age-group - student, service holder, business person, and the homemaker with various experiences in online shopping for a personal interview, and they participated in the survey resulting in a 98% response rate. However, after sorting 100, useful and valid responses were used for further analysis. Accumulated data taken through the manual.

**Secondary Data- Published Work is Referring
Data Analysis & Interpretation**

1) Table showing age the group of respondents

Table No. 1

Below 18 yrs.	18-30 yrs.	31-40 yrs.	Above 40 yrs.
4%	82%	10%	4%

Interpretation No. 1

Out of 100 respondents 80%, are in the age group of 18-30, followed by the age group of 31-40 (10%).

2) Table showing the gender of the respondents.

Table No. 2

Male	38%
Female	62%

Interpretation no. 2

Majority of the respondents were female (62%) followed by the male (38%)

3) Table showing the educational qualification of the respondents.

Table No. 3

Non-matriculate	Matriculate	Graduate	Post graduate
0%	6%	54%	40%

Interpretation No. 3

Majority of the respondents were graduate (54%) followed by students of PG department (40%)

4) Table showing the occupation of the respondent.

Table No. 4

Business/self	Employed service/executive	Student	Others
14%	14%	44%	28%

Interpretation no. 4

Majority of the respondents were a student (44) followed by others (28%)

5) Table showing monthly income of the respondent.

Table No. 5

Less than 5000	5000-10000	10000-25000	25000-50000	Above 50000
48%	10%	16%	20%	6%

Interpretation No. 5

Majority of the respondents has their income of less than 5000(48%) followed by income between 25000 to 50000 (20%)

6) Table showing usage of the internet

Table No. 6

Less than 1 yr	1-3 yrs	3-5 yrs	More than 5 yrs
0%	22%	32%	46%

Interpretation No. 6

Majority of the respondents has been using the internet for 5 yrs. (46%) followed by 3-5 yrs. (32%)

7) Table showing time spent in searching the web

Table No. 7

0-5 hrs.	6-10 hrs.	11-15 hrs.	16-20 hrs.	More than 20 hrs.
50%	14%	12%	10%	14%

Interpretation No. 7

Majority of the respondents are spending time surfing the web are 0-5 hrs. (50%) followed by 6-10 hrs. (14%)

8) Tables were showing online purchases.

Table No. 8

Yes	No
88%	12%

Interpretation no. 8

Majority of the respondents were purchased 88% followed by “No” (12%)

9) Table showing categories of goods bought through the internet

Table No. 9

Convenience goods	Durable goods	Shopping goods	Others
24%	31%	33%	12%

Interpretation No. 9

Majority of the respondents bought shopping goods (33%) followed by Durable goods (31%)

10) Table showing the respondents who have responded for the first time

Table No. 10

Last six months	Six months – 1yr	1-3 yrs.	3-5 yrs.	More than 5 yrs.
36%	6%	22%	18%	18%

Interpretation no. 10

Majority of the respondents were shop last six months (36%) followed by 3-5 yrs. (18%)

11) Table showing how frequently did you purchase online?

Table No. 11

Only once	2-4 times	More than five times	More than six times
20%	38%	12%	30%

Interpretation No. 11

Majority of the respondents frequently purchase 2-4 times (38%) followed by more than six times (30%)

12) Table showing most often accessed the internet

Table No. 12

Home	Office/college	Cyber-cafes	Any other
66%	28%	4%	2%

Interpretation no. 12

Majority of the respondents most often access the internet in the home (66%) followed by office/ college (28%)

13) Table showing the activities that you use the internet.

Table No. 13

communication	Information gathering	Entertainment	Finance	Shopping
33%	11%	18%	18%	20%

Interpretation No. 13

Out of 100 respondents (33%), are used for the activity of communication, followed by shopping (20%).

14) Table showing the categories of goods are you planning to buy through the internet in the shortly

Table No. 14

Convenience goods	Durable goods	Shopping goods	Others
22%	35%	32%	11%

Interpretation no. 14

The majority of the respondents plan to buy Durable goods (35%), followed by shopping goods (32%).

15) Table showing the motivation of purchase through the internet

Table No. 15

Convenience	Price	Save time	Product comparison
65%	20%	10%	5%

Interpretation no. 15

The majority of the respondents motivated the factor of convenience (65%), followed by price (20%).

16) Table showing barrier to purchase online

Table No. 16

Providing personal information	Can't see/touch the product	Hassle of returning the product	Delivery cost too high
36%	28%	23%	13%

Interpretation No. 16

Majority of the respondents having the barrier of providing personal information (36%) followed by can't see/touch the product (28%).

17) Table showing satisfied with the experience

Table No. 17

Highly satisfied	Satisfied	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly satisfied
14%	54%	20%	12%	0%

Interpretation No. 17

The majority of the respondents were satisfied (54%), followed by neither satisfied nor dissatisfied (20%).

Findings of the Study

1. Most of the online shoppers use the internet for searching product information among the categories of goods available online, tickets are the highest category of goods purchased online, followed by computer components, clothes, electronics, fashion accessories, gifts, books, CD/ video, toys, and software.
2. PC and mobile phones are the most popular medium used for internet shopping by Online shoppers.
3. The majority of the respondents that is 97%, agrees that information given about the products on various sites is sufficient for the consumers to purchase them.
4. Among the various options of payment available online, Cash on delivery is the most common method used for payment, whereas bank transfers and personal cheques are the least common method of payment online.
5. The majority of the respondents are satisfied with online shopping.
6. There are some problems faced by online shoppers like delay in delivery, cheap quality of the product, damaged product, etc.

Conclusion and Suggestions

E-commerce has brought a great revaluation in the field of business. Its creating an entirely new economy, which has a potential and it is fundamentally changing the way organizations conduct their business, electronic commerce will become famous. The future of the industry is the online shopping consumer’s daily life to meet their never-ending requirements conveniently. Online shopping is become a new way of life. It has seen by the research because of the value proposition, it offers to a customer such as a convenience, 24x7 shopping, and online shopping is growing to a very great extent as it has made available all kind of product right from basic to the luxury

products which has led to increase in the consumer’s preference for online shopping. Convenience and customer service are the main motivating factors that have seen during the research, which drives the people to online shopping. As a result of today, consumers are buying medical products, gifts, books, movie tickets, travel tickets, home appliances etc. by logging through online, then driving up to a store. As the research suggests, improving in usage of the internet increases online shopping, so there is a need for hikes in broadband penetration as it accelerates the growth of online trade. Observation is made that despite the immense possibilities available on the internet, it is being used for chatting, and surfing. E-mail is the most preferred tool of communication still constitutes in the country’s traffic.

The buyer must provide goods and services at economical price, the seller should be communicating to the buyer about the return policy, shipping policy, the policies related to privacy to the buyer. The seller should also provide increase of after sale facility to the buyer. If required the seller should also educated the customer usage of the product and safety measures that should be taken while the product is being used.

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